

EUROPROJECT
Department [Project Management](#)

D10.2. NAUTILOS Project Website

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Document Control Information

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Deliverable Title	NAUTILOS Project Website
Work Package Title	WP10. Outreach, Communication and Dissemination
Deliverable number	D10.2.
Description	<p>The project's website will include:</p> <p>1) public area - the public area will provide information on the project, the consortium, the project results (including public deliverables etc.) and KER, topic related information, news and links, past and upcoming events, social media links.</p> <p>2) private area (ownCloud) - to facilitate the dialogue and exchange of information within the consortium, hold all the reference documentation that partners will need during the project.</p> <p>The website will function at least 2 years after the project's end.</p>
Lead Beneficiary	EP
Lead Authors	Natali Dimitrova, EP
Contributors	Victoria Geraskova, EP
Submitted by	Gabriele Pieri, CNR
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- Editorial, formatting, and spelling
- Clarification

To request a change to this document, contact the Document Author or Owner.

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Revision	Date	Created by	Short Description of Changes
V0.1	23.03.2021	Natali Dimitrova	First complete draft
V1.0	29.03.2021	Natali Dimitrova	First amended draft
V2.0	30.03.2021	Natali Dimitrova	Final version

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Nature of the deliverable		
R	Report	
DEC	Websites, patents, filing, etc.	✓
DEM	Demonstrator	
O	Other	

Dissemination level		
PU	Public	✓
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

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NAUTILOS - New Approach to Underwater Technologies for Innovative, Low-cost Ocean observation is an H2020 project funded under the Future of Seas and Oceans Flagship Initiative, coordinated by the National Research Council of Italy (CNR, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche). It brings together a group of 21 entities from 11 European countries with multidisciplinary expertise ranging from ocean instrumentation development and integration, ocean sensing and sampling instrumentation, data processing, modelling and control, operational oceanography and biology and ecosystems and biogeochemistry such, water and climate change science, technological marine applications and research infrastructures.

NAUTILOS will fill-in marine observation and modelling gaps for chemical, biological and deep ocean physics variables through the development of a new generation of cost-effective sensors and samplers, the integration of the aforementioned technologies within observing platforms and their deployment in large-scale demonstrations in European seas. The fundamental aim of the project will be to complement and expand current European observation tools and services, to obtain a collection of data at a much higher spatial resolution, temporal regularity and length than currently available at the European scale, and to further enable and democratise the monitoring of the marine environment to both traditional and non-traditional data users.

NAUTILOS is one of two projects included in the EU's efforts to support of the European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy by supporting the demonstration of new and innovative technologies to measure Essential Ocean Variables (EOV).

More information on the project can be found at: <http://www.nautilus-H2020.eu>.

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SUMMARY

The current deliverable presents general information on the website followed by screenshots of the website outlining all website pages. The website has been online since Oct 2020 at the following address: <https://www.nautilus-h2020.eu/>.

The website content will still be updated until the end of the project and 2 years after its end.

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I. GENERAL INFORMATION

At the beginning of the project, in Oct 2020, The NAUTILOS domain name was acquired (www.nautilus-h2020.eu) and the website (initially via a single landing page) was live. As of March 2021, the website was fully developed. In collaboration with all partners and close cooperation with the WP10 leader, EurOcean, EP has designed and developed the project's website and will update and maintain it throughout the project's duration, including 2 years after the project's end. Thus, project partners, key stakeholders and the public will have access to the knowledge and data accumulated during the project even beyond its timeframe.

1. NAUTILOS WEBSITE GOALS AND OBJECTIVES:

The website has the following goals:

- Raise awareness on the project's thematic, objectives, activities and results,
- Increase the visibility of the project and its partners,
- Build understanding of the project's thematic,
- Enable effective communication between the project and external stakeholders, the press and the wider public,
- Enable synergies and engagement with the project's activities, including wider scale engagement for the 5 citizen science campaigns,
- Facilitate the exploitation of the project's results.

2. MONITORING, STATISTICS AND PERFORMANCE

Website's performance, metrics, statistics, trends, and the impact of each activity performed on the website, will be periodically analysed via Google Analytics. This will inform project partners of:

- Unique users count visiting the website,
- Average visit time and bounce rate,
- Languages and locations of visitors,
- Number of page views and average page views per visit,
- Top landing page and bounce rate for different pages.

Google Analytics data will be regularly analysed (every 2 months as part of the internal Work Package Status Reports) and amendments made to improve the user experience.

To improve the user experience and performance in organic search results the website will be optimised via:

- Keywords and meta tags: Primary keywords will be targeted for each website page,
- Content optimisation and submission: page titles are created, strategic search phrases are placed on pages, page URLs will be optimised, title tags will be optimised,
- Social media share buttons will be installed,
- Testing and measuring: active usage of Google Analytics to further improve the website's performance.

II. SITEMAP

The website presents the project in detail through a modern website with the following sub-sections:

- Home
- The Project
 - Overview
 - Activities
 - Objectives
- Partners
- Demonstrations
- Citizen Science
- News
 - News
 - Events
- Resources
 - Promotional Material
 - Newsletter
 - Press Releases
- Contact
- Private Area leading to ownCloud for the partners.

III. HOME

The home page of the website provides access to major sections of the project by scrolling as you can see hereunder:

- A prompt for website visitors to subscribe to the project’s newsletter is placed at the top of the page for better visibility:

Subscribe to our newsletter:

- The website’s navigation tab

- A carousel (slider design) has been placed at the top of the page to display different content with a changing focus based on project developments:

- Reference to the project overview and a quotation by the project coordinator follow:

“NAUTILOS aims to unlock the critical knowledge contained in the ocean over coming decades, and to realise the mutual benefits of marine observation for all element of a sustainable ocean. The flagship H2020 project will develop a new generation of cost-effective sensors and samplers and integrate observation technologies and platforms into large-scale demonstrations across European seas making a significant contribution towards the democratisation of marine environment monitoring.”

Gabriele Pieri, NAUTILOS Project Coordinator

[PROJECT OVERVIEW](#)

- An interactive map (in development) contains references to the partners, the coordinates (if known/applicable) to the demonstrations and citizen science campaigns. Currently the map is in development with the aim being to display hyperlinks and additional information for the specific demonstrations and citizen science campaigns and the partners:

- Reference to the project activities section

NAUTILOS will develop, integrate, validate and demonstrate new cutting-edge marine observation and monitoring technologies.

PROJECT ACTIVITIES

- Reference to the project partners section

NAUTILOS is coordinated by the National Research Council of Italy (CNR) and brings together a multidisciplinary group of 21 entities from 11 European countries

PROJECT PARTNERS

- Footer providing the disclaimer, link to the Data Policy, linkages to the project's social media and project specific contacts (coordinator, communication lead and project manager):

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[Data Policy](#)

Contact

coordination@nautilus-h2020.eu

communication@nautilus-h2020.eu

projectmanagement@nautilus-h2020.eu

IV. DATA POLICY

The data policy opens from the home page's footer and outlines information on how the website will deal with any personal data and comply with GDPR regulation.

Who are we?

NAUTILOS (hereinafter referred to as "NAUTILOS", "we", "us" or "our") is a H2020 project funded under the Future of Seas and Oceans Flagship Initiative. It is coordinated by the National Research Council of Italy (CNR) and brings together a significant group of 21 entities from 11 European countries with multidisciplinary expertise: <https://www.nautilus-h2020.eu/partners/>. Europroject maintains this website ("the Service") on behalf of the NAUTILOS consortium members.

This Data Policy aims to outline how we will deal with any personal data you provide to us while visiting NAUTILOS website. Your privacy and the security of your data are of utmost importance to us. We ensure that we will implement appropriate technical and organizational security measures to protect your information. Yet, keep in mind that no method of transmission over the Internet, or method of electronic storage is one hundred percent secure.

Personal data

While using our Service, we may ask you to provide us with certain personally identifiable information that can be used to contact or identify you ("Personal Data"), such as Email address, first name and last name, Cookies and usage data.

We will handle your Personal Data in accordance with Data Protection Legislation, including Data Protection Acts 1988 to 2018, the General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 ("GDPR"), and any other applicable law or regulation. We will not share Your Personal Data without your consent or unless required by law (except as set out in this Policy). In some circumstances Your Data may be shared with the European Commission in which case Your Data will be processed in accordance with the European Commission Privacy Policy available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/privacy-policy_en.

Usage Data

V. THE PROJECT

The project sections has three subsections:

- Overview

- Activities – overview of the range of activities to be performed during the full timeframe of the project displayed in an interactive format.
 - Main View

ACTIVITIES

- View when additional information has been displayed

- o Objectives – overview of the project’s objectives

OBJECTIVES

- SO1: Develop and demonstrate improved observing systems in coastal and shelf-sea environments
- SO2: Develop and demonstrate improved observing systems in the open ocean and deep-sea environments
- SO3: Develop and demonstrate improved observing systems for anthropogenic debris (i.e. macro-, micro-, nano-plastics)
- SO4: Develop and demonstrate improved observing systems in commercial operations, i.e. fishing vessels, aquaculture facilities, ships of opportunity
- SO5: Develop and demonstrate improved observing systems that utilise animal-borne instruments
- SO6: Quantitatively assess the potential improvements on ocean simulation, ocean forecasting and remote sensing derived from NAUTILOS developments
- SO7: Appropriately collate, process, and archive all primary environmental data generated during NAUTILOS to ensure that it is maximally Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.

VI. PARTNERS

The partners section lists all 21 partners providing additional information on the description of the organisation, the role of the organisation within NAUTILOS as well as providing details on the project's teams.

- Main view

PARTNERS

Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche	Description	+
	Role	+
	Contact	+
	Description	+
	Role	+
	Contact	+

- View when an information on a partner has been displayed

Description -

ETT, SCAI group, is an Italian ICT and creative enterprise. ETT offers innovative and technological solutions to simplify the processes and bureaucracy in the workflow of national and European Public Administration. ETT is the leading company in the creation and supply of information systems for the management of the Italian labour market. In particular, the own-developed-digital platform JUMP (evolution of LINK – Labor Integrated Network), is now used by 60% of public services for employment in Italy, including the Ministry of Labor and Social Policies, 16 Regional administrations and over 50 local administrations.

Role -

ETT S.p.A. will work on Data management and connection services and will be involved in the Dissemination activities. ETT S.p.A. main contribution will be the design and development of the ICT infrastructure (data portal, data ingestion and integration procedures, data flow management) for the discovery, access, and download of the data generated and collected during the project.

Contact -

Antonio Novellino

<http://ett.solutions.com/>

Marco Alba

Susanna Alloisio

VII. DEMONSTRATIONS

Overview of the range of demonstration to be performed during the full timeframe of the project displayed in an interactive format. As additional information becomes available the information will be displayed on a new page for each demonstration.

- Main View

DEMONSTRATIONS

- View when additional information has been displayed

Novel sensor deployments on FerryBoxes and fishery research vessels in coastal regions of Norway and Greece with mariculture and fish farm plants will be utilized. At the same time, DO and chl a sensors from and carbonate system sensors will be in operation at the mariculture and fish farming sites to provide complementary data of higher temporal resolution. Data collected will be QC/QA via a real-time cloud database and used to generate short-term regional forecasts of ocean EOVs and other MSFD-related variables for improving management for sustainable aquaculture. Realtime data stream from underway sensor operations will be utilized to enable real-time event detection from concept change detection, with an adaptive machine learning approach.

AQUACULTURE OBSERVING SYSTEMS

VIII. CITIZEN SCIENCE

Overview of the range of citizen science campaigns to be performed during the full timeframe of the project displayed in an interactive format. As additional information becomes available the information will be displayed on a new page for each citizen science campaign. If applicable – potential volunteers will have the option to subscribe/contribute to the campaign via the website.

- Main View

CITIZEN SCIENCE

- View when additional information has been displayed

IX. NEWS & EVENTS

- News
 - Main view

NEWS

New Approach to Underwater Technologies for Innovative, Low-cost Ocean observation: Launching of the NAUTILOS project

by admin_nautilos | Mar 10, 2021 | News

NAUTILOS Project officially started on the 1st of October 2020 and the KoM will be held virtually on the 21st – 22nd of October 2020. NAUTILOS - New Approach to Underwater Technologies for Innovative, Low-cost Ocean observation is an H2020 project funded under the...

- View when the article has been clicked on

NEW APPROACH TO UNDERWATER TECHNOLOGIES FOR INNOVATIVE, LOW-COST OCEAN OBSERVATION: LAUNCHING OF THE NAUTILOS PROJECT

NAUTILOS Project officially started on the 1st of October 2020 and the KoM will be held virtually on the 21st – 22nd of October 2020.

NAUTILOS – New Approach to Underwater Technologies for Innovative, Low-cost Ocean observation is an H2020 project funded under the Future of Seas and Oceans Flagship Initiative, coordinated by the National Research Council of Italy (CNR), that brings together a significant group of 21 entities from 11 European countries with multidisciplinary expertise ranging from ocean instrumentation development and integration, ocean sensing and sampling instrumentation, data processing, modelling and control, operational oceanography and biology and ecosystems and biogeochemistry, water and climate change science, technological marine applications and research infrastructures.

- Events

Information in this section is still not available. Once it becomes available it will be displayed as a calendar.

- Current view

Q Search for events Find Events List Month Day

< > Today **Now onwards** ▾

 There are no upcoming events.

< Previous Events

Next Events >

[+ Export Events](#)

X. RESOURCES

Resources section contains information on the promotional material (open to download), newsletters and press releases.

- Promotional Material – reference and easy download of project’s related visual material include logos (variations), introductory presentation and other marketing collateral as they become available

PROMOTIONAL MATERIAL

NAUTILOS Logo Variations

Download

Introductory Project Presentation

Download

- Newsletter – to be added when the first newsletter has been released
- Press releases – project-related press releases

PRESS RELEASES

Press Release Nr. 1 – New Approach to Underwater Technologies for Innovative, Low-cost Ocean observation: Launching of the NAUTILOS project

NAUTILOS Project officially starts on the 1st of October 2020 and the KoM will be held virtually on the 21st – 22nd of October 2020. NAUTILOS - New Approach to Underwater Technologies for Innovative, Low-cost Ocean observation is an H2020 project funded under the...

XI. CONTACT

Conventional contact submission form is included with an “I am not a robot” feature as an alternative to the e-mail contacts given on the footer of the home page.

CONTACT US

Name	Email Address
Message	
5 + 13 = <input type="text"/>	
<input type="submit" value="Submit"/>	

XII. PRIVATE PARTNER SPACE

- Link to the project's ownCloud (internal partner space) is available via website's navigation tab

Home The Project ▾ Partners Demonstrations Citizen Science News ▾ Resources ▾ Contact Login →

- View when the link is opened

XIII. APPENDIX 1: REFERENCES AND RELATED DOCUMENTS

Deliverable 10.3 has been developed in accordance with the provision outlined within the following related documents:

- NAUTILOS Grant Agreement Nr. 101000825,
- NAUTILOS Consortium Agreement.

Alongside to these key documents, this has been produced following the European Commission guidelines and templates. Finally, this document will be complementary to other project deliverables and plans such as D1.1 Report on Management procedures (M2), D10.1 Outreach, Communication & Dissemination Strategy (M2), D1.3 Data Management Plan (M6).

ID	Reference or Related Document	Source or Link/Location
1	NAUTILOS Grant Agreement Nr. 101000825	NAUTILOS ownCloud
2	NAUTILOS Consortium Agreement	NAUTILOS ownCloud
3	D1.1. Report on Management Procedures	NAUTILOS ownCloud
4	D10.1. Outreach, Communication and Dissemination Strategy	NAUTILOS ownCloud